

1 **Cloud-based Building Information Modelling (CBIM): Software Engineers' Insights into** 2 **Improving Asset Information Quality**

3 4 **Abstract**

5
6 **Purpose:** This research investigates the capabilities of CBIM in managing quality asset
7 information, drawing upon software engineers' perspectives. Compelling statistics highlight the
8 relationship between building information and environmental sustainability. However, despite
9 the growing utilisation of CBIM in the Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC)
10 industry, a significant knowledge gap remains concerning its effectiveness in maintaining quality
11 asset information.

12
13 **Design/methodology/approach:** This study employed an exploratory qualitative approach,
14 utilising semi-structured interviews with thirteen software engineers actively developing
15 technological solutions for the AEC industry. Following thematic analysis, the findings are
16 categorised into four dimensions: strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and technological
17 limitations. Subsequently, these findings are analysed in relation to previously identified
18 information quality problems.

19
20 **Findings:** This research reveals that while CBIM improves project coordination and information
21 accessibility, its effectiveness is challenged by the need for manual updates, vulnerability to
22 human errors, and dependency on network services. Technological limitations, notably the
23 absence of automated updates for as-built drawings and the risk of data loss during file
24 conversions in the design phase, coupled with its reduced capability to validate context-specific
25 information from the user's viewpoint, emphasise the urgent need for managerial strategies to
26 maximise CBIM's capabilities in addressing information quality problems.

27
28 **Originality/value:** This study augments the understanding of CBIM, highlighting the
29 managerial implications of a robust information management process to safeguard information
30 integrity. This approach fosters sustainable practices anchored in reliable information essential
31 for achieving desired outcomes. The findings also have broader managerial implications,
32 especially for sectors that employ CBIM as an instrumental tool.

34 KEYWORDS: Cloud-based BIM, asset information quality, information quality, sustainable
35 information management, built environment

36

37 **1. Introduction**

38 Buildings stand at the forefront of the global energy challenges. More than just structures,
39 they significantly contribute to energy consumption and carbon emissions, representing 40% of
40 global energy use and over 30% of worldwide CO₂ emissions, higher than the transportation and
41 industrial sectors (Kiamili *et al.*, 2020; Roberts *et al.*, 2018; Santos *et al.*, 2019). The United
42 States Department of Energy reports that approximately half of the energy used in buildings is
43 for heating and cooling. Addressing this issue, the World Green Building Council has set
44 ambitious targets: a 40% reduction in embodied and net-zero operational carbon by 2030,
45 progressing to net-zero carbon for the entire lifecycle of buildings by 2050 (Roberts *et al.*, 2020;
46 World Green Building Council, 2019). These goals are vital for building sustainable practices in
47 the building industry, as the environmental impact of today's construction choices will have
48 long-term consequences (Durdyev *et al.*, 2022).

49 In this context, quality asset information is integral to driving environmental sustainability
50 practices. Originally gathered at the handover phase of a building construction project, this
51 information provides essential asset information about the building (Pinheiro, 2019). Initially
52 static, this information evolves dynamically in response to various projects throughout the
53 building's lifecycle, requiring adequate information management to be effective (Leygonie,
54 2020). Accurately updated asset information is indispensable for maintenance and operational
55 support while achieving the expected life of buildings (Chang *et al.*, 2022). This information is
56 intricately linked to environmental sustainability activities in buildings. Martins *et al.* (2019)
57 argue how asset information can mitigate environmental damage or, if managed inadequately,
58 intensify it. For example, poorly maintained equipment consumes more energy and emits more
59 harmful residues than well-maintained ones (Karpook and Meric, 2023). Given the complexity
60 of building systems and elements, Yalcinkaya and Vishal Singh (2014) underscore the growing
61 importance of dependable asset information as a key enabler for various environmental
62 sustainability initiatives.

63 From an information management perspective, the growing adoption of Building Information
64 Modelling (BIM) holds significant potential for augmenting the quality of asset information.

65 BIM excels during the project delivery phase by creating a compressive suite of essential asset
66 details, spanning spatial zoning to individual components. Its capabilities include generating
67 extensive non-graphical information, such as error-reducing spreadsheets, through various
68 extensions and plugins (Pärn and Edwards, 2017). This wealth of information proves invaluable
69 in the use phase, including energy monitoring and sustainability management (Wong *et al.*,
70 2018). BIM's advanced data storage and ability to produce reliable, in-depth information mark it
71 as a key player in improving building operations. Matarneh *et al.* (2019a) highlight BIM's
72 emerging role, underscoring its transformative impact on building management and maintenance,
73 steering them toward enhancing sustainability.

74 BIM's ubiquitously quoted tangible benefits have recently been amplified by integrating
75 cloud-computing technologies. These advancements have shifted traditional desktop solutions to
76 the cloud, fostering greater collaboration and more efficient information flow during the design
77 phase. Despite these tangible benefits, the quality of asset information continues to pose a
78 persistent challenge, as Shalabi and Turkan (2017) noted. Moreover, manual data entry is
79 necessary for many building information management systems due to the lack of automated
80 information updates, leading to frequent human errors and omissions (Kumar and Lin, 2020). As
81 CBIM becomes prevalent in the building sector, a notable knowledge gap emerges regarding its
82 effectiveness in managing quality asset information during the use phase of buildings. This gap
83 leads us to the central research question:

84 ***To what extent can CBIM ensure the quality of asset information during the use phase of***
85 ***buildings?***

86 To address this research question, this study employs an exploratory approach to investigate
87 CBIM's information management capabilities from the software engineer's viewpoint. This
88 approach is unique yet important for uncovering the inherent technological limitation of CBIM
89 and understanding how to utilise this technological solution to enhance the quality of information
90 effectively. These insights are then cross-referenced with the existing information quality
91 problems, providing a fresh perspective on CBIM's effectiveness in managing quality
92 information. The results of this research enhance the current knowledge of CBIM and provide
93 practical and actionable contributions beyond the building sector.

94 The study is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the extant literature on cloud
95 computing, BIM, CBIM and the concept of information quality. Section 3 outlines the

96 methodology used to assess CBIM’s capabilities in information management through the lens of
97 software engineers. Section 4 presents the research findings. Section 5 discusses the key
98 findings, theoretical contributions, practical implications, limitations of this study and future
99 research directions based on the findings. Finally, Section 6 presents the conclusions drawn from
100 this research.

101 **2. Literature Review**

102 2.1. Cloud-based Building Information Modelling (CBIM)

103 Digital transformation has become an invaluable process for improving the productivity of
104 the AEC industry, which is highly fragmented and involves data-intensive processes across the
105 supply chain and lifecycle (Singh, 2019). BIM represents the modelling techniques used to
106 produce, communicate, analyse, and store information about buildings throughout their design,
107 construction, and serviceable life. Specifically, through access to accurate object-oriented
108 information at the correct time, BIM facilitates an integrated design and construction process,
109 resulting in high-quality buildings at lower costs and reduced project duration. It also supports
110 improved facility management (FM) and future refurbishment of buildings (Sacks *et al.*, 2018).
111 Serving as a shared knowledge source and storage, BIM can reduce the need for redundant data
112 collection and reformatting, leading to more efficient data storage and information exchange and
113 reduced costs associated with the lack of interoperability, automation of checking and analysis,
114 etc.

115 BIM enables modern construction projects to be complex and complicated, requiring
116 collaboration among various subcontractors for seamless data sharing throughout a project’s
117 lifecycle (Alreshidi *et al.*, 2016; Ghaffarianhoseini *et al.*, 2017). Traditionally, desktop-based
118 BIM has faced challenges in maintaining model consistency and integrity, hindered by
119 coordination demands, interoperability issues among different software tools, and difficulties in
120 handling ongoing modifications and manual changes (Sacks *et al.*, 2022). Cloud computing
121 emerges as a solution, enabling on-demand delivery of configurable computing resources over
122 the Internet. This transition from desktop to server-based processing enhances the utilisation of
123 limited resources like computing power and storage. Integrating BIM with cloud computing
124 fosters efficient, cross-domain collaboration, ensuring a unified and consistent BIM model.
125 Additionally, it reduces the operational and maintenance costs of computing infrastructure. As
126 indicated by Zhao and Taib (2022) and other studies, CBIM will become the predominant

127 method, leveraging cloud computing's advantages. This evolution in BIM application promises
128 enhanced collaboration and efficiency in complex construction projects and safeguards the
129 quality of asset information.

130 Compared with conventional BIM, CBIM offers opportunities for improving cross-domain
131 and cross-organisation data storage, information exchange, and remote access, supporting
132 collaboration among multiple parties. Afsari *et al.* (2016) categorise three classifications of data
133 flow architectures used to enable the CBIM:

- 134 1. Manual transfer: This involves the labour-intensive transfer of vendor-neutral file-based
135 BIM (e.g., Industry Foundation Classes (IFC), IFC in short), which, despite being
136 cumbersome, is the most prevalent method for information exchange.
- 137 2. BIM server technology: This approach uses a single-source data server for data sharing
138 among project partners. Its limitation is the centralisation of BIM files on one server,
139 leading to potential bottlenecks and scalability issues.
- 140 3. Data interchange hub: this technology automates data flow between applications through
141 a hub, which synchronises data changes from different participants.

142 Various companies and academic institutions have developed CBIM solutions, such as Autodesk
143 BIM360, Trimble Connect, BIMserver, and Bentley i-Model (Wong *et al.*, 2014).

144 Table 1 shows the recent CBIM literature, highlighting their purpose, adopted BIM format,
145 data transmission process, and the addressed information quality problems. BIM data can be
146 represented, stored, and exchanged in different formats in collaborative BIM-based processes.
147 The IFC standard, a neutral data format, enhances BIM interoperability across platforms. Model
148 View Definitions (MVDs) also facilitate specific data exchange requirements between platforms.
149 An alternative approach utilises semantic web technology for representing building information,
150 such as spaces, assets, and construction processes. This approach offers flexibility in
151 representing and combining data from different domains into computer-readable graphs, enabling
152 efficient federation. In cloud-based data transmission, several protocols are used for effective
153 Internet exchange. These include the basic Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol
154 (TCP/IP), Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) and File Transfer Protocol (FTP). These
155 protocols support a range of data formats, from complete IFC models to specific IFC MVDs or
156 BIM sub-graphs, varying in data size based on the application, software, and intended use cases.

157 The application perspective includes examining CBIM technologies that facilitate collaboration,
158 practices encouraging or hindering team collaboration, and data governance strategies for secure
159 and efficient data usage (Mutis and Mehraj, 2022).

160 **Table 1. The applications of CBIM and the addressed information quality problems.**

161 2.2. Information Quality

162 While BIM, whether desktop-based or cloud-enabled, has been proven as an efficient and
163 collaborative method for managing and storing information in project delivery and the use phase,
164 it is important to note that the technology itself does not automatically assure the quality of the
165 embedded information (Pärn *et al.*, 2016). Since essential building information predominately
166 originates from construction projects, the effective realisation of sustainability objectives through
167 BIM hinges critically on the quality of information fed into the system (Pineiro, 2019).
168 Subsequently, the management of this information across the entire lifecycle of the physical
169 assets plays a pivotal role in ensuring the success of these sustainability goals.

170 Information quality is a complex and multi-dimensional concept without a universally
171 accepted set of dimensions and related definitions of each dimension (Wand and Wang, 1996;
172 Woodall *et al.*, 2013). The quality of information is assessed based on its ability to consistently
173 meet user expectations and requirements (e.g., sustainability), a subjective measure that varies by
174 context (Pringle *et al.*, 2002; Strong *et al.*, 1997; Wang and Strong, 1996). Effective information
175 management addresses this through the entire information lifecycle, including its creation,
176 organisation, storage, distribution, and use (DAMA International, 2017). Commonly cited
177 dimensions in literature are accuracy, completeness, consistency, and timeliness (Chang *et al.*,
178 2022; Woodall *et al.*, 2013):

- 179 • Accuracy: Information reflects the actual value.
- 180 • Completeness: All required information is present to meet the user's requirements.
- 181 • Consistency: The absence of difference when comparing multiple information.
- 182 • Timeliness: Information is sufficiently current for the task at hand.

183 Further elaborating on information quality problems, Ge and Helfert (2007), drawing from
184 previous studies, classified information quality issues into two categories: (1) context-
185 independent and context-dependent. Context-independent problems are those that occur
186 irrespective of the specific situation or application, including issues like spelling errors, data

187 omission, duplications, inconsistent formats, and incorrect values (Eppler, 2006; Oliveira *et al.*,
188 2005). Conversely, context-dependent problems are those that arise in response to specific
189 situational or contextual factors, with violation of company and government regulations serving
190 as a prime example (Pipino *et al.*, 2002). Additionally, the same authors evaluated these issues
191 from two distinctive lenses: the user perspective, which focuses on problems identified by
192 information consumers, and the data perspective, which addresses issues that are inherent to the
193 data itself, independent of any specific user's viewpoint (See Table 2).

194 **Table 2. Categorisation of information quality problems**

195 Leveraging the information quality problems listed in Table 2, this study explores CBIM's
196 contributions to preventing quality deterioration and ensuring the quality of asset information.

197 **3. Methodology**

198 This research argues that inductive theory generation on CBIM capabilities requires an in-
199 depth understanding of CBIM's inherent limitations through those who help develop this tool.
200 Therefore, this research employed a mono-method qualitative approach, leveraging semi-
201 structured interviews with software engineers. A sample of software engineers proficient in
202 developing technological solutions for the AEC industry was selected. This deliberate choice
203 facilitated an in-depth analysis of their unique viewpoints, providing technological capabilities
204 and efficiency of CBIM in handling quality asset information.

205 3.1. Sampling and recruitment

206 Using the purposive sampling technique described by (Lucas, 2014), this study engaged 13
207 participants from software solution providers in the US, UK, Finland and Germany. To ensure
208 that the sample represents the population, potential participants were required to develop
209 technological solutions for the AEC industry, with a specific focus on cloud technology. Table 3
210 details the profiles of the participants engaged in the interviews.

211 3.2. Data collection

212 Semi-structured interviews were chosen as the primary data collection method. Interviews
213 were more valuable than the survey in meeting the aim of this study because they allowed
214 participants to share experiences on the subject under investigation. Before the interviews, the
215 questions were systematically categorised into three main groups: (1) the advantages of
216 leveraging CBIM for effective information management, (2) the prevalent technological barriers
217 faced by CBIM, and (3) the ramifications of employing CBIM in the domain of asset information

218 management. Questions about the advantages of CBIM were instrumental in illuminating its
219 strengths and potential openings for innovation and improvement. Subsequently, questions
220 addressing technological challenges revealed the limitations intrinsic to CBIM, especially
221 concerning managing diverse asset information predominately rooted in current technological
222 constraints.

223 **Table 3. List of participants**

224 Participants had the option to skip questions deemed irrelevant or sensitive, particularly those
225 proving current product development specifics. Interviewing continued until data saturation was
226 reached, meaning no new information emerged from participants, as Easterby-Smith *et al.* (2021)
227 suggested. Interviews averaged 60 minutes. With prior consent, all interviews were recorded
228 and later transcribed for detailed analysis.

229 3.3. Data analysis

230 The data analysis followed the steps of thematic analysis recommended by Gioia *et al.*
231 (2013). Firstly, the interviews were coded using NVivo, a qualitative analysis software,
232 augmented by extensive notetaking to transform the raw data into 69 preliminary concepts. Each
233 researcher performed independent coding of the interviews reflecting the terminology used by
234 participants. Next, the researchers refined the coding scheme. Subsequently, the study
235 performed a data reduction process, eliminating redundant concepts, discarding categories
236 irrelevant to the research question, and merging categories into 16 second-order themes (Gioia *et al.*
237 *al.*, 2013; Grodal *et al.*, 2021). The final cycle culminated in consolidating these themes into 4
238 broader dimensions: strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and technical limitations.

239 To demonstrate the data analysis process, Figure 1 provides an example from an interview,
240 illustrating the steps involved in processing interview data. Initially considered raw data, the
241 interview transcript undergoes categorisation into ‘first-order concept’, which emerges as 69
242 categories from an analysis of 13 interviews. These first-order concepts are further refined into
243 ‘second-order themes’, such as ‘Innovation’, ‘Data Management’ and ‘Technology Constraints’,
244 totalling 16 themes. These second-order themes are then evaluated to identify ‘Strengths’,
245 ‘Weaknesses’, ‘Opportunities’, and ‘Technological Limitations’.

Figure 1. An example of thematic analysis of an interview

247 Significant insights were distilled from the raw data, transitioning software engineers’
248 feedback into an interpretive analysis that enriches understanding of CBIM’s ability to manage
249 quality asset information.

250 4. Results

251 This section presents CBIM's capabilities in managing quality asset information from the
252 perspective of software engineers. Findings are derived from thematic analysis of interviews
253 with anonymous coding (e.g., RQ3P1 and RQ3P2) to maintain confidentiality.

254 Adopting a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis, findings are
255 categorised into Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Technological Limitations, with
256 ‘Threats’ adapted to ‘Technological Limitations’ to better align with the focus of this study.
257 Figure 2 illustrates the findings. Further, linking these findings with the information quality
258 problems identified by Ge and Helfert (2007) are displayed in Figure 3.

259
260 Figure 2. The capabilities of CBIM from software engineers’ viewpoint

261 4.1. Strengths

262 The participants have identified three compelling strengths of CBIM, underscoring its vital
263 role in enhancing asset information quality within the building sector: (1) enhanced collaborative
264 design phase, (2) robust digital storage, and (3) accessibility.

265 The participants indicate that CBIM enhances ‘*collaboration during the design phase*’,
266 leading to generating quality design in construction projects (RQ3P1). As RQ3P12 elucidated,
267 ‘*CBIM can orchestrate the multi-faceted information among the diverse project elements.*’ The
268 collaboration among project participants streamlines workflows, while fostering cross-domain
269 collaboration to allow ‘*each [design element] is uniquely identified, and its details are accurately*
270 *represented in consistent manners*’ (RQ3P3). This collaborative approach fosters the systematic
271 representation of asset information, tailoring the uniqueness of each asset while distinctly
272 expressing design details coherently (Liu *et al.*, 2020; Sacks *et al.*, 2022).

273 Another notable strength of CBIM as its innate ability for digital information storage, which
274 integrates ‘*naturally in the cloud-based environments*’ (RQ3P4). In this context, CBIM adeptly
275 provides ‘*a single source of information containing multiple layers of mechanical, electrical, and*
276 *architectural information*’ in contrast to traditional compilations of information (RQ3P1). This
277 system, acting as a robust repository for asset information, RQ3P2 underscored accessibility
278 offered by CBIM, stating, ‘*Cloud-based BIM enables us to find a vast amount of information*
279 *while providing easy access to those needs*’ information. Moreover, ‘*When a new employee is*
280 *onboard, one can just sort through the CBIM to find the necessary information*’ (RQ3P2).
281 Further, utilising CBIM as a centralised repository can reduce the risk associated with the loss of
282 tangible information, such as drawings.

283 4.2. Weaknesses

284 CBIM offers considerable benefits, yet it simultaneously introduces a set of challenges.
285 Participants have pinpointed key weaknesses: (1) an inability to define information management
286 processes, (2) human errors due to the reliance on manual processes, and (3) the dependency of
287 networks and servers. These shortcomings highlight managerial implications within the domain
288 of CBIM.

289 Although adopting technological solutions can enhance efficiency when using them
290 appropriately, they do not inherently establish an associated ‘*workflow*’ (RQ3P7). Effective
291 workflows are the structural pillars of any organised process, vital for executing tasks efficiently
292 and uniformly. RQ3P2 notes that ‘*I feel strongly that technological solutions [software] do not*
293 *define the workflows.*’ Without well-defined workflows, asset information management via
294 CBIM might not reach its full potential (RQ3P2). The lack of a methodical approach heightens
295 the risk of introducing errors and operational inefficiencies, undercutting the potential benefits of

296 the technology (RQ3P7). Consequently, while CBIM presents an opportunity to advance
297 operational efficiency, it is incumbent upon organisations to devise and implement bespoke,
298 robust workflows designed to align with and amplify the strengths of CBIM. As a result,
299 software engineers asserted the need for a robust *'internal information management procedure'*
300 to prevent the risk of information quality deterioration (RQ3P3, RQ3P5, RQ3P8, RQ3P11, &
301 RQ3P13).

302 Additionally, CBIM's reliance on manual updates jeopardises asset information quality. As
303 RQ3P7 indicates, *'All design elements are manually created during the design phase.*
304 *Consequently, the quality of these design elements is directly proportional to the designers'*
305 *expertise and attention to detail.'* Even during the use phase, CBIM depends on manual updates
306 of existing asset information corresponding to various building projects, which are prone to
307 *'human errors and oversights'* due to the lack of automated information update processes
308 (RQ3P3). This deficiency is especially pronounced in the upkeep of as-built drawings, which are
309 essential for accurate building representations as they guide various activities, including
310 maintenance, renovations, and physical space management. Continuous quality assurance
311 measures among project participants are necessary, requiring designers involved in each building
312 project to approve the quality of handover information before it is updated.

313 Finally, the dependency on networks and servers is recognised as an additional weakness of
314 CBIM. Continuous network connectivity emerges as a foundation for CBIM efficacy, where
315 disruptions can cripple system functionality, a situation that is particularly acute in regions with
316 inconsistent internet services (RQ3P8 and RQ3P10). Server dependency further compounds this
317 risk. Server outages can result in a complete loss of access to vital asset information, leading to
318 halted workflows and asset management activities. RQ3P12 also notes the critical risk of
319 information loss stemming from server crashes. These dependencies introduce substantial risks
320 of operational delays and inefficiencies. As such, there's a pressing need for CBIM to develop
321 resilient data management capabilities, including *'implementing redundant system'*, *'crafting*
322 *offline functionality'* or *'exploring decentralised data storage solutions'* (RQ3P6, RQ3P7 and
323 RQ3P13).

324 4.3 Opportunities

325 RQ3P4, RQ3P9, and RQ3P10 collectively highlighted the transformative opportunity in
326 facilitating a 'drawing-less process' in the submittal procedures. The traditional submittal

327 process, characterised by a sequential approval mechanism required prior to fabrication
328 commencement, is undergoing transformative changes. *‘For example, the contractor can submit*
329 *structural details, such as the I-beam and associated connector details, directly through CBIM*
330 *for the structural engineer’s approval without generating hard copies of submittal drawings and*
331 *the associated material specifications. ‘The accessibility of 3D models on laptops and tablets*
332 *has revolutionised the submittal process’, as articulated by RQ3P4. Additionally, once*
333 *submittals receive approval, they are readily available in an electronic format for fabrication*
334 *purposes. RQ3P10 further stated that ‘this shift towards a drawing-less [object-based] process is*
335 *substantiated for national highway projects in the Nordic countries’.* This exemplifies the
336 opportunities and efficiencies offered by digital submittal processes in the building industry
337 facilitated by CBIM. It markedly reduces potential issues related to information quality and
338 guarantees the effective distribution of information across stakeholders.

339 4.4. Technological Limitations

340 Despite CBIM’s innovative opportunities, software engineers pointed out technological
341 constraints in managing asset information quality: (1) a lack of an automated process of updating
342 as-built drawings and (2) information loss during the file conversion.

343 RQ3P1 elucidated, *‘The concept of CBIM is using BIM software on cloud services, without*
344 *appropriate automated information flow processes. If it is a string of characters [non-graphical*
345 *information], you could easily manipulate to update the information using Excel, but when it*
346 *comes to drawings, it is different’.* *We currently do not have an automated process for updating*
347 *as-built drawings to reflect onsite modifications.’* To illustrate this point, non-graphical
348 information, such as the models, makers, and serial numbers of installed building components,
349 can be extracted into a tabular format, such as an Excel spreadsheet, to facilitate transferring
350 purposes. However, any modifications to the current as-built drawings require updates within
351 the original file format, such as a Revit model. Countering this perspective, RQ3P9 presents the
352 *‘point cloud scanning technique’.* However, this method encounters limitations, including
353 extensive data processing time, scalability, and its restriction to capturing spatial information,
354 omitting essential details in enclosed areas, such as pipes behind walls or above ceilings.

355 In addition, RQ3P6 elaborated on inherent problems of information loss due to technological
356 constraints. This problem is exemplified in the process of *‘converting a 3-dimensional model to*
357 *a 2-dimensional plan, where the conversion fails to transfer the embedded information within the*

358 *objects to the plan*’, underscoring a significant challenge posed by technological constraints.
359 Typically, a 3D model is converted into 2D plans in AutoCAD format, which are widely utilised
360 for construction and space utilisation purposes. However, it is crucial to understand that while
361 dimensional modifications and configurational updates of 2D plans in AutoCAD format may
362 capture spatial alterations, they do not synchronise updates related to essential attributes, such as
363 wall types and thickness, in the corresponding 3D model. Delving this issue with a technical
364 lens, RQ3P3 illustrated a prevalent information issue of information loss through practical
365 applications: *‘Using IFC, for example, we first map data from source X to IFC Y, and then when*
366 *reading data from IFC to application Z, we do another conversion. There are two opportunities*
367 *for information loss. Even if the information could be presented both in X and Z but not in the*
368 *intermediary format Y, the information is lost even though a direct link between X and Z could*
369 *perform the mapping*’. This explanation highlights the challenge of maintaining coherent and
370 up-to-date asset information across different model formats.

371 4.5. CBIM’s capabilities to address information quality problems

372 This section provides an analysis of CBIM’s effectiveness in addressing the quality issues
373 identified by Ge and Helfert (2007), as depicted in Figure 3. The analysis suggests that CBIM is
374 proficient in correcting context-independent data issues such as spelling and syntax errors. Yet,
375 its effectiveness is less assured when it comes to complex problems like the absence of necessary
376 data or incorrect values, indicating a need for improving data validation functions. From the
377 user’s standpoint, CBIM is effective in providing access, retrieval, and secure storage of
378 information, facilitating fundamental user interactions. Nevertheless, it struggles with
379 transforming data into more user-friendly formats without compromising data integrity,
380 reflecting a crucial area for enhancement. These observations signal that while CBIM
381 competently addresses certain information quality issues, it requires further refinement to meet
382 the demands of context-independent information management and user experience.

383 Conversely, Figure 3 reveals that there were no specific information quality issues directly
384 attributable to CBIM from the context-dependent data perspective. However, it becomes evident
385 that CBIM is limited to resolving information quality problems to meet specific situations or user
386 requirements. This shortfall calls attention to the need to optimise resource distribution, analyse
387 business challenges, re-engineer processes, and re-align information flow from sources to
388 address problems effectively (Ge and Helfert, 2007).

389

390

Figure 3. A summary of CBIM's capabilities in asset information management

391

392

The SWOT analysis reveals various dimensions of CBIM's capabilities while highlighting its ability to validate context-dependent user perspective issues requires managerial oversight.

393

394 5. Discussion

395

This research has elucidated CBIM's capabilities in addressing information quality problems through the lens of software engineers developing technological solutions for the AEC industry. Understanding the intrinsic technological limitations is vital for optimising its potential in information management. Building on these insights, this section discusses contributions to theory and practice, acknowledges methodological limitations and provides suggestions for future studies.

400

401 5.1. Theoretical contribution

402

The theoretical contribution of this research lies in its deep exploration of the dynamic interplay between CBIM and asset information management, specifically addressing the complex challenges faced in preventing factors leading to the deterioration of handover information quality. This research acknowledges the capabilities of CBIM in enhancing collaborative design practices, a point underpinned by the findings of Sacks *et al.* (2022), yet it goes further to identify and theorise on the operational challenges, particularly the risk of information loss

407

408 during the design phase due to data conversion across disparate BIM software formats (Sacks *et*
409 *al.*, 2018). These operational challenges are not merely technical issues; they reflect deeper
410 systemic issues faced in the AEC industry, as argued by (Singh, 2019). For example, when
411 multiple BIM applications are involved, the incompatibility between data structures can lead to
412 significant information deterioration. This is not just a technological limitation of CBIM; it also
413 poses a substantial risk to the reliability of handover information, which is critical for the
414 operational integrity of physical assets (Matarneh *et al.*, 2022).

415 As such, this research proposes an ‘Integration Theory of CBIM and Asset Information
416 Management’, which advocates for a lifecycle-oriented approach to information quality. This
417 approach recognises the necessity of integrating CBIM practices within a broader asset
418 management strategy to align with the quality expectations of information users (Ge and Helfert,
419 2007). It advocates for context-specific processes that integrate CBIM, enabling automated
420 quality control mechanisms that utilise advanced analytics, machine learning, and artificial
421 intelligence to not only reactively identify but also proactively predict and mitigate potential
422 deterioration in information quality (Zabin *et al.*, 2022; Zhang, 2020). Moreover, the theory
423 introduces the concept of adaptive learning systems embedded within CBIM, which are designed
424 to refine information management practices by learning and evolving based on ongoing feedback
425 and information. This adaptability is crucial in a field characterised by constant change and
426 evolution, where asset information must be as dynamic and responsive as the environments in
427 which it is applied.

428 By proposing this theory, the research seeks to broaden the existing theoretical landscape of
429 asset information management to include elements specific to CBIM, such as the capacity for
430 real-time updates, the cultivation of collaborative environments beyond the design phase, and the
431 strategic use of digital twins to optimise the management of physical assets. The theory
432 positions CBIM not as a mere repository or static tool but as a dynamic facilitator of asset
433 management, potentially bringing about significant enhancements in the efficiency of asset
434 management, sustainability, and adaptability. In envisioning a holistic integration of CBIM
435 within asset management, this research sets forth a theoretical framework that aims to provoke a
436 paradigm shift toward more efficient and sustainable practices in the built environment. This
437 paradigm shift requires overcoming significant challenges, including ensuring interoperability

438 across diverse BIM tools, developing predictive analytics for quality control, and fostering an
439 industry-wide acceptance of these advanced methodologies.

440 5.2. Practical relevance

441 Grounded in the ‘Integration Theory of CBIM and Asset Information Management’, this
442 theory advocates for a lifecycle-centric approach underpinned by continuous adaptation and
443 feedback mechanisms. These mechanisms are essential for enhancing asset information quality
444 through CBIM. A practical application of this theory is developing an advanced collaborative
445 platform designed to support CBIM activities. From the perspective of technological solution
446 providers, this innovation facilitates using cloud-based storage to support multiple products from
447 the same company, eliminating the need to transfer project data from one solution to another.
448 Such an approach reduces errors caused by human intervention and the potential loss of
449 information during the file import and export processes. Simultaneously, this model enables
450 end-users to leverage analytics for various asset management activities, fostering informed
451 decision-making underpinned by quality asset information. This paradigm shift propels asset
452 management from traditional, static practices to dynamic, feedback-driven processes that are
453 emblematic of adaptive learning principles.

454 Moreover, managing as-built drawings can benefit from incorporating automated quality
455 control mechanisms that resonate with the proposed theoretical insights. Innovations such as
456 CBIM plugins utilising emerging scanning techniques to automate updates to as-built drawings
457 are pivotal. They can mirror real-time modifications, aiming to minimise manual processing for
458 drawing updates, reduce human errors, and ensure the quality of as-built drawings.

459 Further, overcoming challenges related to internet connectivity, especially in less developed
460 or rural areas, involves harnessing the capabilities of digital twin technologies. This approach is
461 bolstered by advancements in 5G technology and the anticipation of 6G networks. It aligns with
462 the theory’s advocacy for real-time updates and collaborative environments, illustrating the
463 practical application of theoretical concepts into tangible, actionable strategies. Integrating
464 digital twins with CBIM optimises the asset management process, rendering it more efficient,
465 sustainable, and adaptable to the evolving dynamics of the built environment.

466 Embedding these practical recommendations presents a visionary strategy for employing
467 CBIM in asset management. It illustrates how theoretical insights can catalyse significant
468 practice transformation, establishing a new standard for efficiency, sustainability, and

469 adaptability in the built environment. Beyond the AEC industry, sectors such as civil
470 engineering, infrastructure, transportation, aviation, manufacturing, real estate, urban planning,
471 and smart city initiatives stand to benefit from these recommendations. Implementing these
472 recommendations promotes an environment where the potential of CBIM can be fully realised,
473 facilitating various activities with quality asset information.

474 5.3. Limitations and suggestions for future research

475 The exploration of CBIM in the AEC industry, primarily from software engineers'
476 perspectives, presents vital insights into its capabilities and limitations within asset information
477 management. However, this concentration limits the exploration to a singular viewpoint,
478 potentially missing the broader spectrum of challenges and opportunities perceived by the end
479 users, such as asset management professionals. While rich in detail, this research's qualitative
480 nature constrains the conclusions' scalability and generalisability. Notably, the technical hurdles
481 highlighted, including information loss during file conversions and the absence of automated
482 updates for as-built drawings, underscore the need for technological advancements and highlight
483 the complexity of implementing CBIM in real-world scenarios.

484 Future research into CBIM must broaden to include diverse stakeholder perspectives,
485 including end-users and regulatory bodies, enhancing insights into CBIM's utility during the use
486 phase of buildings. Integrating quantitative methodologies, such as surveys and case studies,
487 will complement existing qualitative insights, offering a detailed view of the effects of CBIM on
488 asset information quality and operational efficiency. Addressing technological advancement is
489 critical, focusing on developing algorithms and machine learning techniques for automating
490 information updates and minimising information loss during file conversions. This technological
491 push should be accompanied by efforts to enhance software interoperability, ensuring consistent
492 information quality throughout the asset's lifecycle. Moreover, constructing comprehensive
493 frameworks for CBIM implementation and conducting longitudinal studies will be vital. This
494 framework should incorporate best practices for information management and stakeholder
495 collaboration, while longitudinal studies could reveal CBIM's long-term sustainability and
496 economic benefits, providing a holistic view of its potential enhancement and efficiency.

497 **6. Conclusions**

498 This study critically evaluated the application of CBIM in the building sector, focusing on its
499 capabilities in managing information quality, as perceived by software engineers. Key findings

500 of this research indicate that while CBIM can address context-independent quality problems such
501 as spelling errors and digital storage, it requires additional managerial oversights and strategic
502 operational adjustments to exploit its potential fully. A comparative review of these findings
503 with existing literature reveals that although adopting CBIM is widespread in the AEC industry,
504 the focus largely remains on technological advancements rather than on its integration into
505 broader information management processes, a discrepancy that highlights a significant area for
506 future research. This study extends the current understanding of CBIM's capabilities by
507 highlighting the necessity for continuous quality assurance and adopting advanced technological
508 strategies to overcome CBIM's limitations. Moreover, it emphasises the importance of refining
509 CBIM integration strategies and procedural optimisations to address these challenges effectively.
510 Therefore, strategic management and continuous improvement are crucial to address its
511 operational vulnerabilities and maximise its capabilities to improve handover information
512 quality.

513 **7. Acknowledgement**

514

515 **References**

- 516 Afsari, K., Eastman, C. and Shelden, D. (2016), “Cloud-Based BIM Data Transmission: Current
517 Status and Challenges”, presented at the 33th International Symposium on Automation
518 and Robotics in Construction, Auburn, AL, USA, doi: 10.22260/ISARC2016/0129.
- 519 Alreshidi, E., Mourshed, M. and Rezgui, Y. (2016), “Cloud-Based BIM Governance Platform
520 Requirements and Specifications: Software Engineering Approach Using BPMN and
521 UML”, *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, Vol. 30 No. 4, p. 04015063, doi:
522 10.1061/(ASCE)CP.1943-5487.0000539.
- 523 Chang, J., Garcia, J., Xie, X., Moretti, N. and Parlikad, A. (2022), “Explaining Underlying
524 Causes for the Degradation of Handover Information for Commercial Building Owners”,
525 *In World Congress on Engineering Asset Management*, Springer International Publishing,
526 pp. 561–570.
- 527 DAMA International. (2017), *DAMA-DMBOK: Data Management Body of Knowledge (2nd
528 Edition)*., 2nd Edition., Technics Publications, LLC, Denville, NJ, USA.
- 529 Durdyev, S., Ashour, M., Connelly, S. and Mahdiyar, A. (2022), “Barriers to the implementation
530 of Building Information Modelling (BIM) for facility management”, *Journal of Building
531 Engineering*, Vol. 46, p. 103736, doi: 10.1016/j.jobe.2021.103736.
- 532 Easterby-Smith, M., Jaspersen, L., Thorpe, R. and Valizade, D. (2021), *Management and
533 Business Research*., 7th edition., SAGE, Thousand Oaks, California.
- 534 Eppler, M.J. (2006), *Managing Information Quality: Increasing the Value of Information in
535 Knowledge-Intensive Products and Processes*, 2nd ed., Springer, Berlin ; New York.
- 536 Ge, M. and Helfert, M. (2007), “A Review of Information Quality Research.”, *In Proceedings of
537 the 12th International Conference on Information Quality*., presented at the The 12th
538 International Conference on Information Quality., pp. 76–91.

539 Ghaffarianhoseini, A., Tookey, J., Ghaffarianhoseini, A., Naismith, N., Azhar, S., Efimova, O.
540 and Raahemifar, K. (2017), “Building Information Modelling (BIM) uptake: Clear
541 benefits, understanding its implementation, risks and challenges”, *Renewable and*
542 *Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Vol. 75, pp. 1046–1053, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2016.11.083.

543 Gioia, D., Corley, K. and Hamilton, A. (2013), “Seeking Qualitative Rigor in Inductive
544 Research: Notes on the Gioia Methodology”, *Organizational Research Methods*, Vol. 16
545 No. 1, pp. 15–31, doi: 10.1177/1094428112452151.

546 Grodal, S., Anteby, M. and Holm, A.L. (2021), “Achieving Rigor in Qualitative Analysis: The
547 Role of Active Categorization in Theory Building”, *Academy of Management Review*,
548 Academy of Management, Vol. 46 No. 3, pp. 591–612, doi: 10.5465/amr.2018.0482.

549 Karpook, D. and Meric, S. (2023), *Facility Management and Sustainability: A Fundamental*
550 *Alliance*, Planonsoftware.com.

551 Kiamili, C., Hollberg, A. and Habert, G. (2020), “Detailed Assessment of Embodied Carbon of
552 HVAC Systems for a New Office Building Based on BIM”, *Sustainability*,
553 Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute, Vol. 12 No. 8, p. 3372, doi:
554 10.3390/su12083372.

555 Kumar, V. and Lin, E. (2020), “Conceptualizing ‘COBieEvaluator’: A rule based system for
556 tracking asset changes using COBie datasheets”, *Engineering, Construction and*
557 *Architectural Management*.

558 Leygonie, R. (2020), *Data Quality Assessment of BIM Models for Facility Management*, Ecole
559 de Technologie Superieure Universite du Quebec, Montreal, 29 September.

560 Liu, Wang, Q., Gan, V.J.L. and Peh, L. (2020), “Envelope Thermal Performance Analysis Based
561 on Building Information Model (BIM) Cloud Platform—Proposed Green Mark

562 Collaboration Environment”, *Energies*, Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute,
563 Vol. 13 No. 3, p. 586, doi: 10.3390/en13030586.

564 Lucas, S.R. (2014), “Beyond the existence proof: ontological conditions, epistemological
565 implications, and in-depth interview research”, *Quality & Quantity*, Vol. 48 No. 1, pp.
566 387–408, doi: 10.1007/s11135-012-9775-3.

567 Martins, V.W.B., Rampasso, I.S., Anholon, R., Quelhas, O.L.G. and Leal Filho, W. (2019),
568 “Knowledge management in the context of sustainability: Literature review and
569 opportunities for future research”, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Vol. 229, pp. 489–500,
570 doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.354.

571 Matarneh, S., Danso-Amoako, M., Al-Bizri, S., Gaterell, M. and Matarneh, R. (2019), “Building
572 Information Modeling for facilities management: A literature review and future research
573 directions”, *Journal of Building Engineering*, Vol. 24, p. 100755, doi:
574 10.1016/j.job.2019.100755.

575 Matarneh, S., Elghaish, F., Rahimian, F.P., Dawood, N. and Edwards, D. (2022), “Automated and
576 interconnected facility management system: An open IFC cloud-based BIM solution”,
577 *Automation in Construction*, Vol. 143, p. 104569, doi: 10.1016/j.autcon.2022.104569.

578 Mutis, I. and Mehraj, I. (2022), “Cloud BIM Governance Framework for Implementation in
579 Construction Firms”, *Practice Periodical on Structural Design and Construction*,
580 American Society of Civil Engineers, Vol. 27 No. 1, p. 04021074, doi:
581 10.1061/(ASCE)SC.1943-5576.0000652.

582 Oliveira, P., Rodrigues, F. and Rangel Henriques, P. (2005), *A Formal Definition of Data Quality*
583 *Problems., Proceedings of the 2005 International Conference on Information Quality*,
584 *ICIQ 2005*.

585 Pärn, E., Edwards, D. and Sing, M. (2016), “The Building Information Modelling trajectory in
586 facilities management: A review”, *Automation in Construction*, Vol. 75, pp. 45–55.

587 Pärn, E.A. and Edwards, D.J. (2017), “Conceptualising the FinDD API plug-in: A study of BIM-
588 FM integration”, *Automation in Construction*, Vol. 80, pp. 11–21, doi:
589 10.1016/j.autcon.2017.03.015.

590 Pinheiro, S.V. (2019), *Requirements Specification to Enable Efficient Environmental and Energy*
591 *Operation of Buildings*, PhD, University College Dublin, Dublin, October.

592 Pipino, L.L., Lee, Y.W. and Wang, R.Y. (2002), “Data quality assessment”, *Communications of*
593 *the ACM*, Vol. 45 No. 4, pp. 211–218, doi: 10.1145/505248.506010.

594 Pringle, M., Wilson, T. and Grol, R. (2002), “Measuring ‘goodness’ in individuals and healthcare
595 systems.”, *British Medical Journal Publishing Group*, Vol. 325 No. 7366, pp. 704–707.

596 Roberts, C., Pärn, E., Edwards, D. and Aigbavboa, C. (2018), “Digitalising asset management:
597 concomitant benefits and persistent challenges”, *International Journal of Building*
598 *Pathology and Adaptation*, Vol. 36 No. 2, pp. 152–173, doi: 10.1108/IJBPA-09-2017-
599 0036.

600 Roberts, M., Allen, S. and Coley, D. (2020), “Life cycle assessment in the building design
601 process – A systematic literature review”, *Building and Environment*, Vol. 185, p.
602 107274, doi: 10.1016/j.buildenv.2020.107274.

603 Sacks, R., Eastman, C., Lee, G. and Teicholz, P. (2018), *BIM Handbook: A Guide to Building*
604 *Information Modeling for Owners, Designers, Engineers, Contractors, and Facility*
605 *Managers*, Third Edition., John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey.

606 Sacks, R., Wang, Z., Ouyang, B., Utkucu, D. and Chen, S. (2022), “Toward artificially intelligent
607 cloud-based building information modelling for collaborative multidisciplinary design”,
608 *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, Vol. 53, p. 101711, doi: 10.1016/j.aei.2022.101711.

609 Santos, R., Costa, A.A., Silvestre, J.D. and Pyl, L. (2019), “Integration of LCA and LCC analysis
610 within a BIM-based environment”, *Automation in Construction*, Vol. 103, pp. 127–149,
611 doi: 10.1016/j.autcon.2019.02.011.

612 Shalabi, F. and Turkan, Y. (2017), “IFC BIM-Based Facility Management Approach to Optimize
613 Data Collection for Corrective Maintenance”, *Journal of Performance of Constructed
614 Facilities*, Vol. 31 No. 1, p. 04016081, doi: 10.1061/(ASCE)CF.1943-5509.0000941.

615 Singh, V. (2019), “Digitalization, BIM ecosystem, and the future of built environment: How
616 widely are we exploring the different possibilities?”, *Engineering, Construction and
617 Architectural Management*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print, doi: 10.1108/ECAM-
618 01-2018-0004.

619 Strong, D., Lee, Y. and Wang, R. (1997), “Data quality in context.”, *Communications of the
620 ACM*, Vol. 40 No. 5, pp. 103–110.

621 Wand, Y. and Wang, R. (1996), “Anchoring data quality dimensions in ontological foundations”,
622 *Communications of the ACM*, Vol. 39 No. 11, pp. 86–95, doi: 10.1145/240455.240479.

623 Wang, R. and Strong, D. (1996), “Beyond Accuracy: What Data Quality Means to Data
624 Consumers”, *Journal of Management Information Systems*, Vol. 12 No. 4, pp. 5–33, doi:
625 10.1080/07421222.1996.11518099.

626 Wong, J., Wang, X., Li, H., Chan, G. and Li, H. (2014), “A review of cloud-based bim
627 technology in the construction sector”, *Journal of Information Technology in*

628 *Construction*, International Council for Research and Innovation in Building and
629 *Construction*, Vol. 19, pp. 281–291.

630 Wong, J.K.W., Ge, J. and He, S.X. (2018), “Digitisation in facilities management: A literature
631 review and future research directions”, *Automation in Construction*, Vol. 92, pp. 312–
632 326, doi: 10.1016/j.autcon.2018.04.006.

633 Woodall, P., Gao, J., Parlikad, A.K. and Koronios, A. (2013), *Classifying Data Quality Problems*
634 *in Asset Management*, Vol. 19, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-09507-3_29.

635 World Green Building Council. (2019), “Advancing Net Zero Status Report”, May, available at:
636 <https://worldgbc.org/article/advancing-net-zero-status-report-2019/>.

637 Yalcinkaya, M. and Vishal Singh. (2014), “Building Information Modeling (BIM) for Facilities
638 Management--Literature Review and Future Needs”, Unpublished, doi:
639 10.13140/RG.2.1.3052.5525.

640 Zabin, A., González, V.A., Zou, Y. and Amor, R. (2022), “Applications of machine learning to
641 BIM: A systematic literature review”, *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, Vol. 51, p.
642 101474, doi: 10.1016/j.aei.2021.101474.

643 Zhang, G. (2020), “A data traceability method to improve data quality in a big data
644 environment”, *IEEE Fifth International Conference on Data Science in Cyberspace*
645 (*DSC*), IEEE, pp. 290–294.

646 Zhao, Y. and Taib, N. (2022), “Cloud-based Building Information Modelling (Cloud-BIM):
647 Systematic literature review and Bibliometric-qualitative Analysis”, *Automation in*
648 *Construction*, Vol. 142, p. 104468, doi: 10.1016/j.autcon.2022.104468.

649